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Exploring The Impact Motion Corrected Floating Lidar TI On Annual Energy Production

IEA Task 52 AGM

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Motivation

- FLS TI departs differs from point TI measurements; motion and averaging effects
- Uncorrected FLS -> artificially higher TI in the resource assessment
- Large push towards developing better correction methods for TI
- How effective is this correction in applications such as energy production models?
- Well defined KPIs exists for HWS and WD but TI is yet to be fully defined (*Carbon Trust, 2025*)

Scope

- Review concepts relevant to turbulence, FLS, and AEP
- Monte Carlo: propagate measurement errors of TI distributions into AEP uncertainty.
- Quantify change in AEP P_{50} (accuracy) and P_{90}/P_{50} ratio (confidence)
- Present the contextual importance of this uncertainty

Wind Resource Assessments Uncertainties

Measurement uncertainty is **Epistemic & Aleatoric**

Today we will discuss the epistemic component of floating lidar

(Lee & Jason Fields, 2021)

- ✓ A **3%** loss factor equality **1GW** has an estimated cost of **50-60 million EUR** (DNV, 2019)
- ✓ Increases in P_{90}/P_{50} reduces the LCOE (DNV, 2016)
- ✓ Reducing uncertainty by **1%** can result in **USD 0.5 - 2 million** of economic benefits (Brower et al., 2015; Bodini et al., 2022)
- ✓ A change of **1%** in wind speed uncertainty can lead to a **3% to 5% change in NPV** of a wind farm (Kline, 2019).
- ✓ Modelling flow around masts can reduce wind speed measurement uncertainty from **2.68% to 2.23%**, which translates to **GBP 1.2 million** of equity savings for a 1 GW offshore wind farm in the United Kingdom (Crease, 2019)

Floating Lidar, Motion, And Turbulence

- Floating lidar systems (FLS) have become a mature technology for measuring HWS for offshore WRA
- Hydrodynamic forces on the buoy artificially increases the TI measurement
- Motion correction strategies are now being validated, certified and accepted!

Different designs have different motion

FLS TI Motion Correction

What do the standards say?

DNV-RP-0661 (2023)

- $TI_{MRBE} \pm 10\%$ 0.5% change in AEP
- Based on wake affects from experiment
- Developed for onshore lidar

The Carbon Trust OWA roadmap (2025)

- Stage 2/3 + ;
- X_{TI} , C_{TI} , C_{ti} , R^2_{ti} , TI_{MBE} , TI_{RMSE} , TI_{RMBE} , TI_{RMSRE} , TI_{REP-D}

IEC61400 50-4 (2025)

- Comparing the wind speed interval binned turbulence from reference and FLS for the test period.

Do I need motion compensation?

Floating Lidar and Turbulence

- Deterministic method from (*Watson et al., 2025*)
- Motion increases the mean and spread
- Correction improved the mean but a high spread remains
 - We are normalising the regression to met mast residual distributions

Fixed CW to Met mast

Corrected to Fixed CW

Raw to Fixed CW

Normal Distributions of TI Errors

Metric	Fixed TI	Fixed Lidar	CW_Raw	CW_Corr	Pulsed_Raw	Pulsed_Corr
Slope to MM (m_{tot})	—	1.158	1.208	1.08	1.459	1.082
Intercept to MM (C_{tot})	—	-0.007	0.028	0.001	0.054	0.005
RMSE	—	0.01	0.05	0.021	0.08	0.018

$$\mathcal{N}_{TI}(m_{tot}x + C_{tot}, RMSE)$$

TI_{base} = 0.05

TI_{base} = 0.1

TI_{base} = 0.2

While we do show both pulsed and continuous wave distributions, **we are not comparing pulsed to CW**, only corrected to raw. Similar findings presented by (Kelberlau *et al.*, 2020)

Annual Energy Production

$$AEP_p = \sum^{N_T} AEP_{T_i} = \sum n_t \Delta t \int P_{T_i}(x_i) \eta_i(x_i) f(x_i) dx_i$$

- n_t = 8760 [hours]
- $f(x_i)$ = Joint distribution of wind condition at the turbine [U, θ]
- x_i = HWS and WD averaged over a time step Δt
- Δt = Averaging period
- $\eta_i(x_i)$ = Wake losses at the turbine
- $f(x_i)$ = Long term wind resource distribution
- $P_{T_i}(x_i)$ = Power output of the turbine
- N_T = Number of turbines

- These distributions are commonly created from Weibull wind speed distributions interannual variability (*IEC 61400-12-1*)
- P_{50} and P_{90} (shown as P_{70}) values provides banks confidence in the estimation on the AEP of the farm. (*DNV, 2016*)

AEP KPIS

$$P_{90} / P_{50} = (3879 / 3928) = 0.988$$

A measure of uncertainty or confidence

Annual Energy Production

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AEP KPIS

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A measure of uncertainty or confidence

Design (Fatigue)

- The most common use of TI measurements is in the design (*IEC 61400-1*)
- More TI requires more steel which adds cost to a project in numerous ways
- Affects the **LCOE** of the project (out of scope)

Guorui Ren et al., (2018)

Power (AEP)

The effect of TI on power curves at least conceptually well understood (*Kosovi et al., 2025*)

$$\bar{P} = \bar{U}^3 (1 + 3I_u^2)$$

(*Saint-Drenan et al., 2020*)

Increased turbulence increases down stream mix and thus reduces wake losses; increases the power density of a wind farm

Optimal turbine lay is related to the onsite TI measurement (*Liu, 2024*)

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Study Methodology

Monte Carlo Flow Chart

Assume that TI error and Weibull scale parameters are independent and normally distributed / truncated normal

$$AEP_p = \sum_{N_T} AEP_{T_i} = \sum n_t \Delta t \int P_{T_i}(x_i) \eta_i(x_i) f(x_i) dx_i$$

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Results

Case number	Base Ti	Turbine Size	Base Shape mean	Spacing
1.1	0.1	10MW	10.16	7

Results Base Case

- Increase TI uncertainty leads to;
 - Increased AEP P_{50} ; **1 % for Corrected** lidar and **4-7 % for Raw**
 - Reduced P_{90}/P_{50} ratio with **Fixed > 0.99**, **Corrected > 0.98** and **Raw > 0.93**
- Raw Distributions** do not follow a gaussian distribution

Accuracy

Fixed TI vs Other TI Distributions: AEP P50 by TI Uncertainty Model

AEP Distributions by TI Uncertainty Model

Confidence

Fixed TI vs Other TI Distributions: AEP P90-P50 Spread by TI Uncertainty

Sensitivity Analysis

P₅₀ % Error

AEP P₅₀ % Errors

Corrected: 0.5% < P₅₀ < 2%

Raw : 2% < P₅₀ < 12%

P₉₀ / P₅₀

P₉₀ / P₅₀ Confidence

Corrected: 0.97 < P₉₀ / P₅₀ < 0.985

Raw : 0.89 < P₉₀ / P₅₀ < 0.98

All lidar cases increase the AEP P₅₀ compared to a **Fixed TI** value
In all cases corrected lidar offers improvements over raw lidar
Fixed lidar confidence is equivalent to **Fixed TI** confidence

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Discussion

AEP Uncertainty and Confidence

Thinking broader:

$$\sigma_{FLS} = \frac{(1 - P_{90}/P_{50})}{1.282}$$

	Fixed Lidar	Corrected	Raw
P_{50} change	<1%	<2%	<12%
P_{90}/P_{50}	>0.98	>0.97	>0.89
σ_{FLS}	1.56%	2.24%	8.58%

*'For offshore wind farms currently in development, DNV GL would typically expect to see a 10-year P90/P50 ratio of the order of **88% to 92%**' (DNV, 2019)*

Combining, in quadrature, FLS uncertainty and Base AEP uncertainty using (JCGM,2008; IEC 61400-12-2:2022)

AEP Uncertainty: 7.95% (Fixed), 8.14% (Corrected), 11.60% (Raw)

- Using FLS TI in AEP estimations, then the
 - **Raw TI contributes >3%** compared to fixed
 - **Corrected TI contributes 0.2%** compared to fixed
- Interannual variability contributes **6%** (Pryor, 2018)

Summary: Is The Correction Good Enough?

- Corrected TI measurements bias AEP P_{50} by 0.5-2%, slightly higher than DNV-0661
- AEP uncertainty from corrected TI increases by 0.2% compared to fixed lidar
- Where should we focus the efforts of further correction?
 - Bias means more accurate corrections required
 - Machine learning and better access to data
 - Metmast equivalent TI
 - Characterising sensitivities and models of FLS TI errors (motion, wind speed, stability)
 - Apply 50-4 method to better model TI measurement errors
- Better measurements do lead to better modelling outputs (*Klemmer et al., 2024*)
- Opportunity to use in-situ TI measurements from FLS; needs evidence of maturity
- Presented Preliminary methodology to assess AEP based TI KPIs
- Recommend the DNV AEP method should be update to review FLS and offshore sites

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Thank You Questions?

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Let's Connect!

A number of case studies are run to assess:

- Effect of farm design and site conditions on the uncertainty requirements
- If correction impact is related to site specific conditions

Case number	Base TI	Turbine Size	Base Shape mean	Spacing	Type
1.1	0.1	10MW	10.16	7	BASE
2.1-2.10	0.04-0.2	10MW	10.16	7	Sensitivity
3.1-3.10	0.1	5-15MW	10.16	7	
4.1-4.10	0.1	10MW	8-12	7	
5.1- 5.10	0.1	10MW	10.16	5-10	

Sensitivity Analysis

AEP P_{50} % Errors

Corrected: $0.5\% < P_{50} < 2\%$

Raw Lidars: $2\% < P_{50} < 12\%$

P_{90} / P_{50} Confidence

Corrected: $0.97 < P_{90} / P_{50} < 0.985$

Raw Lidars: $0.89 < P_{90} / P_{50} < 0.98$

All lidar cases increase the AEP P_{50} compared to a **Fixed TI** value

In all cases corrected lidar offers improvements over raw lidar

Stronger relationship with site resource than the farm design, binned TI KPIs are suitable

Fixed lidar confidence is equivalent to **Fixed TI** confidence

TI measurement uncertainty

Metric	HWS slope	HWS R ²
Stage 2	0.97-1.03	>0.97
Best Practice	0.98 – 1.02	>0.98

CT OWA Roadmap V3 (*The Carbon Trust, 2025*)

No agreed upon threshold but defines 7 parameters to consider for performance

Recommend a single variant regression to fit TI

DNV (*DNV-RP-0661*)

Set the AEP threshold for TI to be an MRBE of +/-10%

Based on wake affects from experiment

'Not for floating lidar'

IEC (*IEC 61400-50-4:2025*)

Wind speed interval binned comparison

Sensitivity study following type and unit qualification

CFARS (*St. Pé, A., et al., 2021*)

90th percentile thresholds

PyWake from DTU is used to model the AEP_p

For each sample the AEP is deterministically calculated based on the input parameters

Turbulent Turbine module

Power Curve

- The power curve is affected by several variables (Kosović et al., 2025)

$$P_{TI} = \int P_{raw}(u) \cdot f(u, v, \sigma) du$$

$$f(u, v, \sigma) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(u-v)^2}{2\sigma^2}}$$

- Turbine size changes the rated wind speed and diameter

Wake model

Considered a few options native to Pywake

- NOJ Turbo Deficit (Nygaard et al., 2020)
 - Considers the turbine TI
 - Similar to Park model (Jensen, 1983; Katić, 1987)
 - Frandsen model: $I(x) = \sqrt{I_0^2 + I_w^2(x)}$, (Frandsen, 2007)

	Power Curve (U ≈ Rated)	Power Curve (U << Rated)	Wake Affect
High TI	Decrease in power	Increase in power	Increase in power
Low TI	Increase in power	Decrease in power	Decrease in power

Farm Module

- Farm design typically comes after the WRA

5D spacing

10D spacing

Regression to PDF

Metric	CW_Corrected
Fixed to MM (m_{MM})	1.158
Fixed to MM (C_{MM})	-0.007
Slope (m_{dem})	1.08
Intercept (c_{dem})	0.007
RMSE	0.02

$$\sigma = RMSE_{u=8m/s}$$

$$c_{tot} = C_{MM} + m_{MM}c_{dem}$$

$$m_{tot} = m_{MM}m_{dem}$$

$$\mathcal{N}_{TI_{CW_{corr}}}(m_{tot}x + c_{tot}, RMSE)$$

Demming regression parameters and RMSE are produced by (Watson et al., 2025)

Metric	Fixed TI	Fixed Lidar	CW_Raw	CW_Corr	Pulsed_Raw	Pulsed_Corr
Slope to Fixed (m_{dem})	—	—	1.043	0.933	1.26	0.934
Slope to MM (m_{Tot})	—	1.158	1.208	1.08	1.459	1.082
Intercept (C_{dem})	—	—	0.03	0.007	0.053	0.01
Intercept (C_{Tot})	—	-0.007	0.028	0.001	0.054	0.005
RMSE	—	0.01	0.05	0.021	0.08	0.018

Results: Convergence

- To validate the number of simulation, converge a convergence study was ran
- The simulation was run for a high variation case
 - Spacing 7D
 - $Tl_{base} = 0.1$
 - $Tl_{dist} = \text{Pulse uncorrected}$
- P90 is the most sensitive to number of simulations
- Values converge at $N = 5000$ simulations

